

ANALYZING THE POEM OF EDGAR ALAN POE

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ABSTRACT

The article learns and analyses the poem which is written by Edgar Alan Poe The Raven. By demonstrating clear explanation of every stanza one by one and opening the meanings and explaining what tried Poe to mean by writing this poem and choosing exactly this situation with a man in the dark cold December night and the raven which knocked the door then window, moreover taking a seat to the statue of Athena the goddess of wisdom, in addition the repetition of word “Nevermore”.

Introduction

„Nevermore“ everyone comprehends this word in their own criteria of thinking, ones consider that it is nonsense word of a talking raven that knows only one word—“Nevermore”, while others like Edgar Allan Poe sees in this scene the world of emotional wars that individuals face on all walks of life and the fight of control over the emotions of grief and loss in this simple situation with a lonely man in the dark night missing his beloved and the bird's answer “Nevermore” appears to the speaker that he is going to live forever in the shadow of the bust of Pallas above his door.

From the first stanza of Poe's The Raven the reader comprehends that the story will be full of drama, the picture of loneliness, the dark and cold December night opens on a “dreary” or boring midnight and a “weak and weary” character. The imaginary of cold and dark midnight demonstrates mystery and suspense for the reader. Already tired and exhausted character introduces a tired out and exhausting story. As we later learn that the

character has suffered a great deal before this poem even begins.

As Poe shifts the narrative from the tapping on the door to the thoughts of the character the air of grey unknown situation continues to build. This could also portray that the character himself is avoiding answering the door. By feeling the situation we can see that Poe is already hinting to the readers the cause of the characters' insecurities.

“Lenore” by this name Poe opens the whole pains and emotional sufferings of the speaker in the poem. We find that the character is pining for Lenore, a woman who was very dear to him (a girlfriend or wife perhaps) whom he can no longer be with as she has died and is in the company of angels. She becomes “nameless” (again underlining the theme of loss) to him because she does not exist in his world anymore. For him, she is forever lost.

The symbolization of purple curtains are easily demonstrates the feeling of character focusing on emotional state and his healing wounds, as this is a color of bruise which is in the beginning stage of recovery. Poe has

provided details of the room and they are described as sad and uncertain.

Finding nothing on the other side of the door leaves him stunned. He stands there staring into the darkness with his mind racing. How could he have heard the clear continuous knocking at the door only to find nothing...physical? Now because he had been pining for Lenore, she quickly comes to mind, so he whispers her name into the empty night 'Lenore?' and an echo whispers back 'Lenore!'

The narrator tried to emphasize how stunned the speaker was at looking into the hardships and suffering of his life showing the scene by the darkness through the wide-opened chamber and his expectations of what he would find. He expected to find a visitor (sympathy) but instead found empty darkness (suffering). Finally the character finds the power to himself and faces the sufferings and memories of Lenore by opening the chamber door and looking to the dark cold December night. To his surprise from his suffering came back a voice saying Lenore and nothing more. This exposes that the sole core of his suffering was truly Lenore and he had to open that door of his self-doubt and weakness to figure it out.

The narrator describes the raven as one who looked rather royal and like it belonged in the righteous or impressive times of the past. The raven does not even acknowledge the speaker, and he simply flies in with the airs of an aristocrat and rests on the statue above the chamber door of "Pallas". Then, it just sits there doing "nothing more"

As an explanation of the title the raven plays the most important in the poem and as it is written the character embraces the realization of the cause of his insecurity by opening the window and the raven comes flying in. This raven is signifying the loss that the character has suffered. Through the window of realization, his loss comes flying in

to face him. The raven is described to be grand in its demeanor, much like the loss of Lenore that intimidates him. The ravens taking seat on the statue of Pallas was an interesting moment the reason why Pallas-Athena goddess of wisdom discloses to the reader that this feeling of loss and grief that the character is feeling is literally sitting on his wisdom. It has overpowered his rational thought.

After speaking that one word, the raven did not utter another word. He sat there on the statue very still and quiet. The narrator returns to his grim mood and mutters about having friends who have left him feeling abandoned, just like this bird will likely do. On hearing this, the bird again says: Nevermore.

Conclusion

Poe underlines the fact that the character has so much more feeling than what he tackles when he confronts his grief. As he contemplates over the concreteness of the words "nevermore" he relapses into memories of Lenore. The cushion symbolizes his connection to his physical life. As he battles with his emotions, the cushion reminds him that his beloved Lenore will never share his physical space and life again. She will never again, physically be in his company.

However, the character lets the reader know that all is not well. The Raven still sits on the statue of Pallas and it looks demon-like whilst casting a shadow that traps him forever.

That is significant because it gives the reader closure. It tells the reader that even though the character welcomed the feelings of loss and grief when he opened the window of realization, he despises them now. These emotions appear to him as demonic. And the shadow the cast over him; meaning the mood that is created from these feelings has a permanent hold on his soul. He has been defeated by his feelings after facing them, and he will find peace: nevermore.

References :

<http://poemanalysis.com> The Raven by Edgar Alan Poe / Edgar Alan Poe

<http://www.litchrts.com> Summary to Edgar Alan Poe The Raven

<http://www.sparknotes.com> The Plot Overview SparkNotes